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What do teachers expect from immigration? Acculturation expectations among compulsory education teachers in Spain

Abstract

Background: Previous research has shown that teachers' beliefs, attitudes, and expectations about cultural diversity, immigration, and immigrants' acculturation processes play an important role in students' psychosocial and sociocultural adaptation. However, few studies in Spain have specifically examined teachers' acculturation expectations toward immigrant populations. **Aims:** This study analysed acculturation expectations among compulsory education teachers in Spain and examined the relative contribution of demographic and psychosocial variables in explaining their variability. **Methods:** An online survey was administered to 320 compulsory education teachers in Spain. Measures assessed support for cultural preservation, assimilation, and separation of immigrants, as well as pro-diversity beliefs, intercultural sensitivity, and negative stereotypes toward immigrants. **Results:** Teachers showed greater support for cultural preservation than for assimilation or separation. Female teachers expressed stronger support for cultural preservation, whereas male teachers showed greater support for assimilation. Younger teachers rejected assimilation and

separation more strongly than older teachers. Cultural preservation support was positively associated with intercultural sensitivity and pro-diversity beliefs, whereas separation and assimilation were associated with negative stereotypes, lower intercultural sensitivity, and weaker pro-diversity beliefs.

Conclusions: The findings suggest that teachers' acculturation expectations are closely linked to their beliefs about diversity, intercultural sensitivity, and attitudes toward immigrant populations. Given the influence of these factors on pedagogical practices and students' adaptation, the results underscore the importance of strengthening teacher training in intercultural competencies, self-reflection, and critical thinking.

Keywords: acculturation expectations; immigration; education; Spain.

Introduction

In a globalised world, where migration is increasingly dynamic, issues about ethnic and cultural diversity are central to political debate in most modern societies. In this regard, governments have developed different responses to manage cultural diversity within their borders, proposing various policies, including restrictive measures, assimilationist policies, or multicultural solutions (Berry et al., 2022).

In the current European Union, for instance, where the percentage of the foreign-born population is around 13.3% (Eurostat, 2024), cultural diversity has been acknowledged as a core principle of the Union in the European Parliament's 2016 Resolution (European Commission, 2016, 2020). This resolution requires member states to implement strategies based on an intercultural integration model, underscoring the significance of inclusive education across all educational levels. However, a detailed examination of the contemporary EU context reveals fragmented and polarised opinions on immigration, leading to discrepancies

concerning integration and interculturality (Blomberg, 2020; Dochow-Sondershaus & Teney, 2024; Simon & Beaujeu, 2018; Zapata-Barrero, 2017).

In Spain, where approximately 14% of the population is of foreign nationality (Instituto Nacional de Estadística (INE), 2025), the Spanish government has also developed several instruments to facilitate access to documentation, education, and health for immigrants (Mahía & Medina, 2022) such as the law on the Rights and Freedoms of Foreigners in Spain and their Social Integration and its implementing Regulation, which guarantee foreign minors' right and duty to compulsory schooling on equal terms with Spanish nationals (Ley Orgánica 4/2000).

Also, Spain have developed the national program that supports educational improvement (Programa para la Orientación, Avance y Enriquecimiento Educativo, PROA+, 2025) providing additional support and resources to educationally vulnerable students, including newly arrived immigrant pupils, to improve school success and prevent early school leaving, and the Ministry of Education's Guidelines for Intercultural Education (Martínez Ambite, 2023), which promotes intercultural and inclusive practices in secondary schools in order to foster the educational inclusion of culturally diverse and migrant students.

The Spanish case is particularly complex due to its territorial organisation based on the sovereignty of each of its 17 autonomous communities and two autonomous cities (Ceuta and Melilla), producing different regulations and guidelines depending on the particularities of each territory and the specific characteristics of the immigrant groups they receive (Rodríguez-Izquierdo, 2018; Rivera-Vargas, 2020).

In addition, negative perceptions of immigrants and their cultural expressions currently occupy a central place in public debate in Spain, contributing to growing social polarisation and increasing support for more restrictive immigration policies, as reflected in mass media and social networks (Fernández-Suárez, 2021; López-Rodríguez et al., 2020).

Within this sociopolitical context, understanding how members of the host society expect immigrant populations to adapt to the larger society becomes relevant. These perceptions are best defined as acculturation expectations, that is, the attitudes and beliefs held by members of the receiving society on how immigrants should relate to and adapt within the mainstream culture (Berry et al., 2022; Smith-Castro et al., 2021, 2023). Acculturation expectations constitute a central dimension of intergroup relations because they can either facilitate or hinder the social integration of immigrant populations (Berry, 2019).

Educational institutions are among the main social contexts in which intercultural contact and acculturation processes occur. As schools become increasingly diverse, teachers play a particularly influential role in shaping the educational and psychosocial experiences of students from immigrant backgrounds by fostering—or constraining—inclusive school environments (Brown et al., 2021; Schachner et al., 2016).

These issues are especially important for the Spanish education sector today, as it is experiencing a notable increase in immigrant students, making Spain one of the countries with the highest classroom diversity in the European Union (European Education and Culture Executive Agency, Eurydice, 2019). The number of foreign students enrolled in non-university education in Spain has grown markedly over the last decade. While in the 2012–2013 school year there were around 760,000 foreign students in non-university programmes (approximately 8–9% of total enrolment), by 2022–2023 this figure was close to one million, representing around 11–12% of the student body in compulsory and post-compulsory education (Ministerio de Educación y Formación Profesional, 2023). Specifically, in compulsory education, the presence of foreign students has also increased substantially: by 2022–2023, foreign pupils already accounted for around 14% of total enrolment in primary education and about 11% in lower secondary education (Ministerio de Educación y Formación Profesional, 2023).

Furthermore, in Spain, more than 25% of educational centres (in primary and secondary education) have more than 10% of students from diverse sociocultural backgrounds (Ministerio de Educación y Formación Profesional, 2020). In other European countries, the percentage of students born abroad ranges from 5% to 15% (European Education and Culture Executive Agency, Eurydice, 2019). In addition, the latest TALIS report indicates that although multicultural self-efficacy among Spanish teachers has increased, there remains a need to strengthen teacher training in the structural aspects of educational inclusion (Ministerio de Educación, Formación Profesional y Deportes, 2025).

Thus, the study of acculturation expectations among teachers represents a pivotal opportunity to understand the intercultural dynamics surrounding the integration of new immigrants in a social context marked by increasing tensions over immigration. As contextualised research on significant predictors of teachers' acculturation expectations, this study addresses two relevant needs in the acculturation and intercultural education literature: (a) it contributes to filling a noteworthy gap in the current literature in Spanish-speaking contexts among the specific population of teachers, and (b) it provides novel evidence to inform public policy.

Specifically, research conducted in Spain in recent years has offered valuable in-depth analyses of teachers' attitudes and expectations towards cultural diversity and acculturation expectations, primarily through small-sample case studies with specific groups in specific communities of the country (Del Carmen Medina Podadera & González-Jiménez, 2023; Rodríguez-Izquierdo, 2021; Sáenz-Hernández et al., 2023). However, there is little systematic evidence on why some teachers hold particular acculturation expectations through multivariate analyses to detect associated factors of these expectations. In addition, there is little research employing standardised measures of acculturation expectations, as previously defined, in larger samples. Therefore, the present study advances knowledge of this phenomenon by

strengthening the replicability of acculturation theory and related explanatory models through a multivariate approach, while also providing evidence to inform educational policies and training programs.

Acculturation expectations: Theory and research

Literature on intercultural contact and acculturation has proposed several models of acculturation expectations (Berry, 2019; Berry et al., 2022; Bourhis, 2017, Navas et al., 2005), where three expectations captured the attention of most studies: (i) Pluralism or Multiculturalism, which represents the expectation that the cultural preservation of traditions and customs must be maintained, respected, and actively promoted; (ii) assimilationism (the Melting Pot), which is based on the idea that immigrants must renounce their cultural particularities and adopt those of the receiving society; (iii) separation, which assumes that the "coexistence" of groups with different ethnic citizenship is only possible if the groups live physically separated.

Empirical research on these expectations shows that citizens of multicultural societies tend to expect immigrants to adopt primarily integration strategies and, secondarily, assimilation or separation strategies; however, in some cases, separation or assimilation is preferred over cultural preservation (Berry et al., 2022; Smith-Castro et al., 2021). Research has also shown that there are different sources of variability in responses to immigration. For instance, some studies have documented that devalued or more culturally distant groups are expected to separate or assimilate more than valued or more culturally close groups, while other studies show that immigrants are expected to integrate and preserve their culture into the domain of social relations and friendships but to assimilate in the domains of work, economics, and values (Batkina et al., 2022), making the valuable distinction between how groups prefer acculturation to occur in the ideal plane (i.e., expectations) and what actually happens during the daily intergroup contact (real plane) (Navas et al., 2005)

Theory and research also show that these expectations are shaped by demographic and psychosocial variables, such as age, education level, income, gender, positive attitudes about cultural diversity, intercultural sensitivity, and perceptions of immigrants and immigration (Berry et al., 2022; Ozer & Kamran, 2023).

Regarding sociodemographic predictors, a recent meta-analysis by Dražanová et al. (2024) found that education significantly affects attitudes toward immigration after controlling for economic factors. They also found that positive attitudes toward immigration were associated with higher skill levels, occupational status, and income, while age emerged as a key factor in their meta-analysis, with older individuals expressing more negative views than younger participants. In contrast, gender, social status, and unemployment did not play a decisive role in immigration attitudes.

Similarly, Kobayashi and Tanaka (2024) found no gender differences in attitudes towards migration in the Netherlands, whereas Lefringhausen et al. (2023) found that women scored significantly higher than men on multiculturalism in England. Furthermore, it has been observed that women's greater support for cultural preservation and men's greater inclination towards assimilation are moderated by various social, cultural, and sex-role factors (Friberg & Jahanlu, 2023; Muchomba & Kaushal, 2022). In general, caution should be exercised when interpreting these results, as they may vary across contexts and specific immigrant groups (Dražanová et al., 2024).

Regarding psychosocial variables, Genkova and Schaefer (2023) found that cultural empathy and flexibility are associated with acceptance of multiculturalism, suggesting that the ability to understand other cultures and adapt to unfamiliar situations can facilitate acceptance of cultural diversity. On the other hand, Ulbricht et al. (2022) found that factors such as support for cultural pluralism, expectations of cultural maintenance, and norms of equality and

inclusion are directly and positively associated with different facets of intercultural self-efficacy.

Finally, the data also show that stereotypes and prejudice are related to national debates about immigration and the expectations of their integration. For example, positive stereotypes have been shown to predict support for policies that facilitate immigration. In contrast, attributions of negative qualities have been shown to predict negative attitudes toward migrant populations and support for restrictive immigration policies (Giannousi, 2025; López-Rodríguez et al., 2014, 2020; Lefringhausen et al., 2023; Smith-Castro et al., 2021, 2023; Teruya et al., 2020).

In general, the literature suggests that support for pluralistic forms of coexistence and expectations of cultural preservation may be linked to greater appreciation of cultural diversity, greater intercultural sensitivity, and fewer negative evaluations. In contrast, the expectation of separation might be associated with a lack of intercultural sensitivity, attitudes against cultural diversity, negative intergroup attitudes. Assimilation expectations have both positive and negative outcomes, with some studies showing that assimilation is linked to prejudice and exclusion, while others show that assimilation expectations are associated with positive attitudes towards migration (Becker, 2019; Cabaniss & Cameron, 2018; Giannousi, 2025; Lefringhausen et al., 2023; Smith-Castro et al., 2021, 2023; Teruya et al., 2020; Whitley & Webster, 2018).

Why Teachers' Acculturation Expectations Matter?

Previous research has shown that teachers' perceptions of immigration are associated with the way they deal with immigrant students, impacting students' performance. Specifically, data show that teachers' attitudes and beliefs about immigration contribute to either hindering or fostering an inclusive atmosphere in educational contexts (Beniscelli et al., 2019; Schachner et

al., 2017). In this regard, understanding how teachers perceive cultural diversity and immigrant populations has become increasingly relevant in intercultural education research.

A recent systematic review of European studies on teachers' perceptions of cultural diversity and inclusion conducted by Semião et al. (2023) showed greater variability in teachers' responses to culturally diverse students. While some teachers adopt inclusive and culturally responsive practices, others perceive diversity (particularly linguistic and ethnic diversity) as a challenge associated with learning difficulties, behavioural problems, or reduced classroom performance. The review further identified the persistence of deficit-oriented and assimilationist perspectives toward certain minority groups, including immigrant, refugee, Muslim, and Roma students. Authors identified insufficient intercultural training and limited institutional support as the key barriers to inclusive education.

Consistent with these findings, other studies show that the type of acculturation students are expected to adopt, as well as the type they actually adopt, constitutes a key factor in their identity development, academic performance, and overall adaptation (Tran & Birman, 2019). Research has also shown that certain teaching practices (e.g., content, methods, and communication) can function as risk factors in students' acculturation processes (Makarova et al., 2019), whereas inclusive educational environments may foster more positive integration outcomes.

Studies conducted in Spain reveal similar patterns. For example, Rodríguez-Izquierdo (2021) found that Andalusian teachers generally endorsed assimilationist and monolingual ideologies toward migrant students' bilingualism, despite expressing positive discursive attitudes toward linguistic diversity. Regular teachers tended to perceive students' home languages as obstacles to academic achievement, whereas language teachers were more likely

to value bilingualism as a resource. Teachers also strongly supported Spanish-only educational approaches and assigned responsibility for maintaining students' home languages primarily to families rather than schools. Similarly, Del Carmen Medina Podadera & González-Jiménez (2023) and Sáenz-Hernández et al. (2023) have identified patterns of biased expectations and assimilationist tendencies among teachers toward certain immigrant groups (i.e. Moroccan and Romanian).

In sum, several studies have shown that teachers' beliefs and attitudes shape their classroom practices. Some attitudes and beliefs may hinder students' sociocultural adaptation, whereas others favour successful adaptation and inclusion. Overall, the evidence strongly suggests that teachers' worldviews, beliefs, expectations, and intercultural training constitute the foundation upon which intercultural competencies are built in educational settings. This underscores the importance of studying key dimensions of intercultural relations in schools, such as teachers' acculturation expectations (Acar, 2023; Alam & Mohanty, 2023; Argüello-Gutiérrez et al., 2025; Dignath et al., 2022).

Objectives and hypotheses

Grounded on acculturation and intercultural education literature, the purpose of this study is twofold: (i) to describe the patterns of acculturation expectations towards immigrants among compulsory education teachers in Spain, and (ii) to test the relative contribution of demographic and psychosocial variables to predict acculturation expectations.

Based on the literature reviewed, support for culturally pluralistic forms of coexistence and the preservation of immigrants' cultural identities is expected to be associated with more positive attitudes toward cultural diversity, higher intercultural sensitivity, and lower levels of prejudice and negative stereotyping. Conversely, separationist expectations are expected to be related to lower intercultural sensitivity, weaker support for cultural diversity, and stronger

prejudicial attitudes and negative stereotypes toward immigrant populations. Therefore, the following hypotheses were tested: Expectations of cultural preservation will be linked to (H1) positive attitudes towards diversity, (H2) high cultural sensitivity, and (H3) low levels of negative stereotypes. On the other hand, separation expectations will be associated with (H4) negative attitudes towards diversity, (H5) low cultural sensitivity, and (H6) negative stereotypes. Given the mixed results of assimilation expectations, no specific hypotheses were tested. Similarly, given the mixed results in regard to the role of demographic variables in acculturation expectations, no hypotheses were advanced for them either.

Methods

The present cross-sectional study is part of the research project DiverProf, which analyses the attitudes and perceptions of compulsory education teachers in Spain towards acculturation and interculturality (see more about the project at http://figshare.com/articles/presentation/Memoria_cientifica_del_proyecto_Diverprof/21477336/1?file=38079648). The current study was motivated by an interest in providing updated data on how Spanish teachers experience the challenges of increasing classroom diversity, focusing on how they expect immigrants to acculturate and which variables predict their acculturation expectations.

Participants

As part of the project mentioned above, 661 teachers and university students of the primary and secondary levels in Spain voluntarily completed the online questionnaire. Participants were recruited via social media platforms, and emails were sent to 44.120 mandatory primary and secondary schools from all autonomous communities of the country (Spanish Ministry of Education and Vocational Training, 2020). For the present study, only active teachers were included, resulting in a sample of 320 primary and secondary school teachers (224 women, 70%) aged 22 to 67 years ($M = 44.89$, $SD = 9.77$). Most participants (78%) worked in public

schools. These characteristics are consistent with the current population of compulsory education teachers in Spain, which has a mean age of 45 years, is 62% female, and includes 74.4% of teachers employed in public schools (Ministerio de Educación, Formación Profesional y Deportes, 2024; Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD], 2025). More specifically, none of the one-sample tests were statistically significant ($t = -0.20$, $df = 319$, $p = .84$; χ^2 for gender = 3.52, $df = 1$, $p = .061$, χ^2 for type of school = 2.42, $df = 1$, $p = .120$)

Instruments

The questionnaire included a sociodemographic section assessing age, gender and professional data, as well as psychometric scales of the variables under study. Unless otherwise specified, all items were answered on a 5-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (completely disagree) to 5 (completely agree). Internal consistency coefficients for the present sample are reported in Table 1.

Pro-diversity beliefs were assessed using the Pro-Diversity Beliefs Scale developed by Kauff et al. (2019), which measures the extent to which cultural diversity is perceived as beneficial and socially valuable. The scale comprises five items. Sample items include: “A diverse society functions better than one that is not”, “A society with a high degree of cultural diversity is better able to tackle new problems”, and “I value cultural diversity in Spain because it benefits the country”. The original validation study was conducted across four samples ($N = 1,450$). Results supported the unidimensional structure of the scale and showed adequate internal consistency coefficients ($\alpha > .90$). Evidence of construct validity was provided through positive correlations with favourable attitudes toward immigrants and ethnic minorities and negative correlations with authoritarianism and perceived threat. Scores were computed by

averaging the five items, with higher scores indicating greater endorsement of cultural diversity and multiculturalism.

Intercultural sensitivity was measured using the Spanish adaptation of the 15-item Intercultural Sensitivity Scale (ISS-15; Wang and Zhou, 2016; adapted by Segura-Robles and Parra-González, 2019). The instrument assesses individuals' affective and behavioral disposition toward intercultural interactions. Example items include: "I often give positive responses to my culturally different counterparts during our interactions", "I feel confident when interacting with people from different cultures", and "I avoid situations where I have to deal with culturally distinct persons" (reverse-scored). Previous research with the Spanish version reported excellent internal consistency ($\alpha = .92$) and adequate convergent validity, with Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values above .65. The global score was calculated by averaging the 15 items, with higher scores reflecting higher intercultural sensitivity, openness, attentiveness, and self-efficacy in intercultural interactions.

Stereotypes toward immigrants were assessed using an index derived from the stereotype content framework proposed by Fiske et al. (2002), expanded by Leach et al. (2007) and López-Rodríguez et al. (2013). The measure evaluated the attribution of warmth-, competence-, and morality-related characteristics to immigrants as a social group. The index included four negative traits (e.g., "aggressive", "malicious") and four positive traits (e.g., "competent", "honest"). Previous studies based on the stereotype content model have reported satisfactory internal consistency coefficients ($\alpha > .80$) and evidence of construct validity through associations with perceived intergroup competition, perceived status, and intergroup evaluations. In the present study, positive traits were reverse-coded before calculating the global index of negative stereotyping with high scores indicating more negative stereotypical attributions towards immigrants.

Acculturation expectations were measured using the 18-item Acculturation Expectations Scale developed by Smith-Castro et al. (2021), grounded in John W. Berry's acculturation framework. The scale assesses prescriptive expectations regarding how immigrants should adapt, participate, and relate to the host society. To capture the normative component of acculturation expectations, participants were instructed as follows: "Please think about immigrants and give us your opinion on how they should live with us". Before the items were presented, respondents also read the introductory statement: "Many problems between Spaniards and immigrants could be solved if...". The scale assesses three dimensions: cultural preservation, assimilation, and separation expectations. Sample items include: "Each group preserves its traditions and customs" (cultural preservation), "They adopt Spanish traditions and customs" (assimilation), and "They live a little apart from us" (separation). The original validation study showed evidence in favor of a three-factor structure, adequate test-retest reliability ($r \approx .60$), internal consistency coefficients above .80, and convergent and discriminant validity, as evidenced by logical associations with the Canadian Multiculturalism Ideology Scale (Berry and Kalin, 1995).

Procedure

A pilot survey was conducted to test the psychometric characteristics of the instruments. The final version of the questionnaire was assembled using the QuestionPro platform and was accessible from March to June 2023. It was announced through social media channels and distributed via email to educators across Spain. Participation was voluntary, and participants were asked to complete an informed consent form presented on the first screen of the online questionnaire. Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board of the Universidad Internacional de La Rioja (UNIR), under code PP-2022-06 and PI:081/2022.

Analyses

Data analyses were conducted using Jamovi Open Statistical Platform (The jamovi project, 2024). The analytical strategy, following the study aims, examined first the general patterns of teachers' acculturation expectations and second the relative contribution of demographic and psychosocial variables to their prediction. For all analyses, statistical significance was set at $p < .05$.

First, descriptive statistics and psychometric analyses were conducted for all study variables to characterise the sample, evaluate response distributions, and assess internal consistency, ensuring the adequacy and reliability of the measures prior to conducting inferential analyses. Second, bivariate correlation analyses were performed to examine the direction and strength of the associations among the variables and to provide an initial assessment of whether the observed relationships were consistent with the study hypotheses.

Finally, three independent multiple linear regression analyses were conducted, with each acculturation expectation as the criterion variable, respectively. Sociodemographic variables (e.g., age and gender) and psychosocial variables (e.g., intercultural sensitivity, pro-diversity beliefs, and negative stereotypes) were entered simultaneously as predictors to evaluate their relative contributions to explaining the variance in each expectation, while controlling for the effects of the remaining variables in the model to identify the unique association of each predictor with the acculturation expectations. Given the cross-sectional and correlational nature of the data, the regression analyses were interpreted as indicators of statistical association rather than evidence of causal relationships.

Prior to conducting the regression analyses, the assumptions of linear regression were evaluated. Data inspection revealed no serious violations. Multicollinearity was assessed using

conservative criteria, with all variance inflation factor (VIF) values below 2 and all tolerance values above .65, falling within the recommended thresholds (VIF < 4; tolerance > .25; Field, 2018).

Results

Following the study's aims and the analytical strategy described before, the results are presented in three main sections: a) descriptive and psychometric analyses, b) bivariate correlations among the variables, and c) the summary of the multiple regression analyses.

Descriptive and psychometric data

Table 1 shows that all scales presented adequate reliability with Cronbach's Alphas ranging from .82 (Intercultural Sensitivity Scale) to .94 (Pro-Diversity Beliefs Scale). The mean scores show that teachers elicited high levels of pro-diversity beliefs, intercultural sensitivity and cultural preservation, mid-levels of assimilation expectations, and low negative stereotypes and separation levels. A within-subjects ANOVA showed significant differences across acculturation expectations, evidencing the highest support for cultural preservation, followed by assimilation, and separation as the least supported expectation, $F_{(2,638)} = 264.13, p < .001, \eta^2 = .34$.

Correlations matrix

The bivariate correlations are presented in Table 1. Examining the correlations among the expectations data shows that cultural preservation was negatively correlated with assimilation and separation, whereas assimilation was positively associated with separation. In other words, high expectations for preservation were associated with low expectations for assimilation and separation, whereas high expectations for assimilation were associated with high expectations for separation.

Focusing on the correlations of each type of expectation with the predictors, Table 1 shows a significant correlation between cultural preservation and gender, as women elicited higher scores on cultural preservation than men. Data also show that cultural preservation expectations were significantly and positively correlated with pro-diversity beliefs and intercultural sensitivity and negatively correlated with negative stereotypes. High levels of cultural preservation were associated with more positive attitudes towards cultural diversity, greater intercultural sensitivity, and fewer negative stereotypes.

On the other hand, significant correlations were observed between assimilation expectations and age and gender; specifically, older teachers had higher assimilation expectations than younger teachers, and women had lower assimilation expectations than men. Data also showed that assimilation expectations were negatively correlated with pro-diversity beliefs and positively correlated with negative stereotypes. In other words, teachers with high assimilation expectations had lower support for diversity in society and higher levels of negative stereotypes than teachers with low assimilation expectations.

Finally, Separation expectations were significantly correlated with age, as younger teachers presented fewer levels of separation than older teachers. Additionally, separation expectations were negatively correlated with pro-diversity beliefs and intercultural sensitivity but positively correlated with negative stereotypes and age. That is, high scores on separation were associated with low scores on pro-diversity beliefs and cultural sensitivity, and with high levels of negative stereotypes.

Multiple regression analyses

Table 2 summarises the multiple regression results. The significant predictors of cultural preservation were gender, pro-diversity beliefs, and intercultural sensitivity. Specifically, being female, having firm pro-diversity beliefs, and having high intercultural sensitivity predicted

high levels of cultural preservation. The model explained 17% of the variance of intercultural preservation expectations.

The significant predictors of assimilation were gender, age, pro-diversity beliefs, and negative stereotypes. Specifically, being older, being a man, having low levels of pro-diversity beliefs, and having high levels of negative stereotypes predicted high levels of assimilation expectations. All variables in this model explained 19% of the variance of this expectation.

Finally, the significant predictors for separation were age, negative stereotypes, and intercultural sensitivity. Being older, attributing negative stereotypes to immigrants, and having low intercultural sensitivity predicted high levels of separation. The model explained 13% of the variance of this expectation.

To sum up, teachers reported high levels of pro-diversity beliefs, intercultural sensitivity, and support for cultural preservation, whereas separation expectations and negative stereotypes were comparatively low. Cultural preservation appeared as the most strongly endorsed acculturation expectation, followed by assimilation, while separation was the least supported orientation. Consistent with H1 and H2, expectations of cultural preservation were positively associated with pro-diversity beliefs and intercultural sensitivity at both the correlational and regression levels. H3 was only partially supported: cultural preservation was negatively correlated with negative stereotypes, but negative stereotypes were not a significant predictor in the regression model. Also, H4 received partial support: although separation expectations were negatively correlated with pro-diversity beliefs, this expectation did not remain significant in the regression analysis after controlling for the remaining predictors. Finally, H5 and H6 were supported, as separation expectations were associated with lower intercultural sensitivity and stronger negative stereotypes in both correlational and regression analyses.

Discussion

Informed by literature on intercultural contact and acculturation in school settings, this study had two primary goals: (i) to describe patterns of acculturation expectations toward immigrants among compulsory education teachers in Spain and (ii) to examine the relative contribution of demographic and psychosocial variables in predicting these expectations. These objectives were guided by the understanding that acculturation expectations constitute key attitudinal dimensions shaping teachers' intercultural competencies and pedagogical practices. Accordingly, the study tested the hypothesis that expectations of cultural preservation would be associated with (H1) positive attitudes toward diversity, (H2) higher intercultural sensitivity, and (H3) lower levels of negative stereotypes. In contrast, separation expectations were expected to be associated with (H4) negative attitudes toward diversity, (H5) lower intercultural sensitivity, and (H6) stronger negative stereotypes toward immigrant populations. Given mixed evidence involving assimilation expectations and demographic variables, no specific hypotheses were formulated for these variables.

Overall, the data supported most of the proposed hypotheses and replicated previous findings in this line of research (Berry et al., 2022; Smith-Castro et al., 2021, 2023). Participants endorsed cultural preservation more strongly than the other acculturation expectations, followed by assimilation, whereas separation emerged as the least supported orientation. Complementarily, teachers reported high levels of pro-diversity beliefs and intercultural sensitivity, along with comparatively low levels of negative stereotypes and separationist expectations toward immigrants.

At the same time, the findings revealed important variability in responses to immigration across sociodemographic and psychosocial factors, yielding differentiated profiles

of acculturation expectations among teachers. Specifically, being female, endorsing stronger pro-diversity beliefs, and reporting higher intercultural sensitivity predicted greater support for cultural preservation. In contrast, being older and male, holding lower pro-diversity beliefs, and expressing stronger negative stereotypes predicted higher endorsement of assimilation and separation expectations.

These patterns have relevant implications for acculturation research and intercultural education models. We first discuss the findings concerning demographic predictors and then turn to psychosocial predictors.

Regarding gender differences, the finding that women supported cultural preservation more strongly than men, while men showed greater support for assimilation than women, is consistent with previous research on gender differences in acculturation expectations (Lefringhausen et al., 2023). Some authors have suggested that men tend to express more negative attitudes toward immigration because they generally report higher levels of authoritarianism and social dominance orientation, whereas women tend to show greater affective empathy and openness toward cultural diversity (El Sayed et al., 2020).

At the same time, other authors have hypothesised that women may reject certain immigrant groups more strongly than men, particularly when these groups are perceived as threatening gender equality (Ponce, 2017). As noted earlier, previous research indicates that the relationship between gender and attitudes toward immigration is complex and context-dependent, varying according to the specific domain of acculturation and the specific immigrant groups under consideration. In the present study, participants evaluated immigrants as a broad social category rather than specific ethnic or cultural groups. Therefore it is not possible to back up any interpretation of gender differences in. Consequently, future research

should further examine how men and women respond to different immigrant populations in order to develop a more nuanced understanding of the meanings attached to immigration and how those meanings shape acculturation expectations from a genderised perspective.

Regarding age, the finding that younger teachers expressed lower endorsement of assimilation and separation expectations than older teachers is also in line with previous research showing that younger populations tend to hold more favourable attitudes toward immigration (Dražanová et al., 2024; Nikleva & Rico-Martín, 2016). In the Spanish context, these findings may reflect broader generational differences in exposure to diversity, as younger cohorts have likely grown up in more globalised and culturally diverse environments. In addition, teacher education in Spain may have increasingly emphasised diversity, inclusion, and interculturality, potentially fostering more open attitudes toward migration and cultural diversity among younger teachers (European Education and Culture Executive Agency, Eurydice, 2019). Data from the present study cannot fully support these interpretations but underscore the need for further research examining the role of intercultural policies and teacher intercultural competences training in shaping their attitudes and practices related to cultural diversity in the classroom.

Turning to psychosocial predictors, cultural preservation was positively associated with intercultural sensitivity and positive appreciation of cultural diversity. In contrast, separation expectations were associated with lower intercultural sensitivity and stronger negative stereotypes. Assimilation expectations shared variance with separation expectations and were characterised by lower support for diversity and stronger negative stereotypes.

The results of assimilation expectations linked to separation and negative stereotypes are consistent with previous studies (Smith-Castro et al., 2021, 2023; Whitley & Webster,

2018) but remain particularly noteworthy. These links may be interpreted in several ways. On the one hand, assimilation expectations may reflect a broader intolerance toward cultural diversity, accompanied by the assumption that immigrants should abandon their cultural distinctiveness and adopt Spanish customs within an idealised framework of cultural homogeneity. On the other hand, assimilation expectations may represent a more subtle form of rejection of immigration, grounded in the false dichotomy that coexistence is only possible if immigrants either assimilate into the host culture or live completely separate from it (common variance with separation).

Also, the expectation of assimilation might be a response to feelings of threat posed by immigrants, especially in the face of greater cultural differences in key values, traditions and religious views, for example. As posited by the Integrated Threat Theory, feelings of threat (both symbolic and realistic) are key predictors of prejudice and negative outgroup evaluations (Stephan & Stephan, 2000). Finally, other authors have hypothesised that the link between assimilation expectations and negative evaluations might result from psychological reactance in contexts where national policies of pluralism exert pressure to conform to multicultural views (Whitley & Webster, 2018). In general, these results highlight the need to continue studying the many meanings and implications of assimilation expectations in the Spanish context.

It is also important to note that not all expected associations remained stable across analytical levels. Specifically, H3 and H4 were supported in the bivariate analyses but were not confirmed in the multivariate regression models after controlling for the remaining predictors. Although negative stereotypes and pro-diversity beliefs were significantly associated with cultural preservation and separation, respectively, in the correlational analyses, some of these

relationships lost significance in the regression models after accounting for the shared contribution of the other predictors.

Taking into account only the significant predictors, regression analyses suggest that support for cultural preservation may be better explained by positive orientations toward diversity and intercultural openness than by the mere absence of negative stereotypes. Likewise, separation expectations appear to be more directly associated with evaluative dimensions of intergroup relations, such as negative stereotyping, than with broader ideological orientations toward diversity, as previous research has shown (Park et al., 2022; Smith-Castro, 2021, 2023; Urbiola et al., 2021).

In this way, our analyses support central assumptions of contemporary acculturation theories by showing two clusters of attitudes, beliefs and expectations, namely a multicultural openness cluster characterized by intercultural sensitivity, positive appreciation of cultural diversity, and support for cultural preservation, and an intergroup rejection cluster characterized by low intercultural sensitivity and negative outgroup evaluations. More specifically, contribute to strengthening acculturation theories and models that conceptualise acculturation as a context-dependent process shaped by multiple psychosocial factors operating at both the actual and the ideal plane and varying according the characteristics of the many actors involved in the contact (Berry, 2019; Berry et al., 2022; Navas et al., 2005).

Practical implications

The findings have important implications for educational policy and teacher training. The data suggest that when immigration is perceived primarily as a threat, teachers may reproduce stereotypes and biases toward immigrant students by promoting assimilationist or separationist expectations. Conversely, when immigration is perceived as an opportunity for intercultural

enrichment, teachers may help foster more inclusive, intercultural educational environments that support the harmonious integration and development of students from immigrant backgrounds (Argüello-Gutiérrez et al., 2023, 2025).

Given the relative contribution of the predictors identified in regression models, particular attention should be devoted to strengthening intercultural sensitivity within teacher education and intercultural competency training. The findings also suggest that teacher training programs should promote self-reflection and critical thinking, considering that teachers' beliefs about cultural diversity and immigration shape their expectations toward students, particularly those from immigrant backgrounds.

Limitations and future research

The study has several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the correlational and cross-sectional design does not allow causal inferences between the variables examined. In addition, the use of self-report online questionnaires may have introduced self-selection and social desirability biases, particularly given the sensitivity of intercultural issues. Despite the fact that the sample resemble the characteristics of the population of Spanish teachers, self-selection bias may limit the generalisability of the findings, as individuals with a greater interest in the topic may have been more likely to participate. Although the instruments showed adequate psychometric properties, constructs such as acculturation expectations may not be fully captured through self-perception measures.

Furthermore, the regression models did not include behavioural or contextual variables—such as prior intercultural training, institutional support, previous experience working with diverse populations, or school-level diversity policies—that may also influence acculturation expectations. Future studies should incorporate these variables and employ

multilevel, longitudinal, or experimental designs to better examine causal relationships and account for potential third variables.

Conclusion

Compulsory education teachers in Spain generally endorsed cultural preservation and positive attitudes toward cultural diversity, while expressing low support for separatist expectations toward immigrants. At the same time, acculturation expectations varied according to both demographic and psychosocial factors. Overall, findings show that teachers' acculturation expectations are closely associated with their beliefs about diversity, intercultural sensitivity, and perceptions of immigrant populations. Given the potential influence of these attitudes, beliefs, and expectations on pedagogical practices and the successful adaptation of students from immigrant backgrounds, the findings highlight the importance of strengthening training in self-reflection and critical thinking for future teachers.

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WHAT DO TEACHERS EXPECT FROM IMMIGRATION?-Submitted version

Table 1. Descriptive, psychometric, and correlational overview of the variables under study.

	%	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	α	Preservation	Assimilation	Separation
Cultural preservation		3.37	0.88	.87	-	-	-
Assimilation		2.49	0.84	.86	-.23***	-	-
Separation		1.82	0.96	.93	-.13*	.32***	-
Gender	70% female	-	-	-	.16**	-.19***	-.01
Age		44.89	9.77	-	.10	.30***	.23***
Pro-diversity beliefs		4.24	0.90	.94	.36***	-.25***	-.14*
Intercultural sensitivity		4.17	0.43	.82	.28***	-.07	-.20***
Negative stereotypes		1.89	0.74	.90	-.22***	.22***	.24***

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$. Gender (0 = male, 1 = female)

WHAT DO TEACHERS EXPECT FROM IMMIGRATION?-Submitted version

Table 2

Summary of the multiple regression analyses

Predictors	Criterion variables								
	Cultural Preservation			Assimilation			Separation		
	<i>B</i>	<i>EE</i>	β	<i>B</i>	<i>EE</i>	β	<i>B</i>	<i>EE</i>	β
Gender	0.22	0.10	.11*	-0.28	0.09	-.15**	-0.00	0.11	.00
Age	0.01	0.00	.08	0.03	0.01	.31***	0.02	0.01	.24***
Pro-diversity beliefs	0.26	0.06	.27***	-0.17	0.06	-.19***	0.01	0.07	-.01
Cultural sensitivity	0.35	0.12	.17**	0.08	0.11	.04	-0.32	0.13	-.14*
Negative stereotypes	-0.01	0.07	-.00	0.15	0.07	.13*	0.25	0.08	.19***
<i>R</i>	.42			.44			.36		
<i>R</i> ²	.17			.19			.13		
<i>F</i> _{5,314}	13.25***			15.18***			9.39***		

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$. Gender (0 = male, 1 = female).